

CNRS, INSERM & UNIVERSITÉ DE LYON
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FRANCE

Data Use Agreement

I request access to the data collected in the digital repository of the Brain, Behavior, and Learning Lab, part of the Lyon Neuroscience Research Center, established at Bron, France (hereinafter referred to as the CRNL), and I agree to the following:

1. I will comply with all relevant rules and regulations imposed by my institution and my government. This may mean that I need my research to be approved or declared exempt by a committee that oversees research on human subjects, e.g., my Institutional Review Board or Ethics Committee.
2. I will not attempt to establish the identity of or attempt to contact any of the included human subjects. I will not link this data to any other database in a way that could provide identifying information. I understand that under no circumstances will the code that would link these data to an individual personal information be given to me, nor will any additional information about individual subjects be released to me under these Data Use Terms.
3. I will not redistribute or share the data with others, including individuals in my research group, unless they have independently applied and been granted access to this data.
4. I will acknowledge the use of the data and data derived from the data when publicly presenting any results or algorithms that benefitted from their use:
 - (a) Papers, book chapters, books, posters, oral presentations, and all other presentations of results derived from the data should acknowledge the origin of the data as follows: "Data were provided (in part) by the Brain, Behavior, and Learning Lab at the CRNL".
 - (b) Authors of publications or presentations using the data should cite relevant publications describing the methods developed and used by the Brain, Behavior, and Learning Lab at the CRNL to acquire and process the data. The specific publications that are appropriate to cite in any given study will depend on what the data were used and for what purposes. When applicable, a list of publications will be included in the collection.
 - (c) Neither the CRNL, nor the researchers that provide this data should be included as an author of publications or presentations if this authorship would be based solely on the use of this data.
5. Failure to abide by these guidelines will result in termination of my privileges to access to these data.

Place and date:

Name and affiliation(s):

Signature:

N.B. Send this signed agreement to jerome.prado@univ-lyon1.fr for access to the dataset.